

PRIORITY TASKS OF INCREASING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF THE ECONOMY OF UZBEKISTAN

Sulaymonov Akmaljon Asadullayevich

Email: intelligence@inbox.ru Tel: +998917705000

ABSTRACT: *This article discusses the main ways to increase the volume of investments in the economy of our country and to create an investment environment.*

KEY WORDS: *investment, innovation, investment environment, innovative method, free economic zone, foreign investments, entrepreneurship, economic development.*

INTRODUCTION

Private entrepreneurship and small business are finding their place in the conditions of accelerating the development of science and technology, transitioning to new technologies in advanced branches of industry. Such entrepreneurship is an integral part of the whole system, which provides work with new information technologies, new ideas and modernization of production. In addition, small enterprises are one of the preferred forms of production in conditions of high risk.

Small enterprises are also very important in introducing technological innovations. Small businesses, which adopt new technological ideas faster than large enterprises, have less risk and can get up and running faster than large-scale manufacturing. And this our science and technology in the conditions progress to develop help to give can of the economy common development supply, commodity and services shortage eliminate in reaching small business and private entrepreneurship big place holds Labor resources fast growing up and work release in the location to himself characteristic conditions in Uzbekistan small enterprises system to the body to bring the following opportunities creates:

- free work resources, new economy of relations current to be made, new ownership of forms appear to be as a result work in release to be discharged of individuals social work to issue more attraction of ownership new forms appear to be
- of the population, the first in line, young people material, spiritual and occupation level raise
- national and artistic craftsmanship recovery as well small and middle 58 enterprises, village population points to develop help show, in general, every one region for great important economy efficiency increase

The economy in development small business and private entrepreneurship positive importance confession reached without, his importance excess evaluate sending is also correct it's not. Private entrepreneurship only certain only during activity show takes, that's it because of small business activities development for necessary the conditions create necessary Of this for in our opinion, different savings organize reach need These are savings entrepreneurs commerce in banks preferential loans get for guarantor to be, subsidies, that's it including back not given to subsidies of the economy separately priority in the fields enterprises development for source being service to do it is necessary

It is known that in the republic to labor capable 65.3 of the population percentage in villages lives This is a village in places of entrepreneurship development for very big opportunities existence shows. That's it with one in a row, a village economy work was busy in the release temporarily worker forces service display, re work and that's it such as directions again distribution need In the village entrepreneurship, his small business forms development with depends different management on the steps organizational, economic issues solution reach priority issues to the line enters

These issues done increase for our country scale the following issues solution reach should:

- market economy conditions work for competitive personnel preparation and their qualification increase
- in the regions real entrepreneurship environment create;
- small business and private entrepreneurship activities financial support;
- small business and entrepreneurship activities legal base strengthening;
- small business and private entrepreneurship activities technological equipment with to provide support;
- reforms the results advertising and information service tools through wide to the public deliver

Today's in the day many developed and the world in the economy leader place holding countries experience that's it without words prove is giving to competition reach and the world to the markets exit the first First, the economy consistent reform achievement, structural in terms of change and diversification to do deepening, high to technologies based on new enterprise and work release networks fast development provide, activity showing powers modernization to do and technical new processes acceleration, that is in our country diversification and modernization to do strategies at the expense of done increase can

In the world happened giving financial and economic crisis conditions entrepreneurship development important important has

Entrepreneurship market economic economy is an activity. Otherwise in other words, it is specific economic to the result reach in order to goods and services design, development release and exchange organize reach according to of the owners or they are representatives conscious and purposeful economic is an activity.

" Uzbekistan in the Republic entrepreneurship about". in the law to entrepreneurship as follows definition given " business - ownership". of subjects benefit get in order to risk by doing and proprietary responsibility based on the current laws within initiative with economic activity is to show "

Entrepreneurship of activity three type and to him typical respectively of entrepreneurship three the group separately show can:

new commodity or the service design organize to achieve Entrepreneurship this type with intellectual property owners - innovation entrepreneurs engaged in, they new commodity and services design, development release processes improve them work to issue current reach on the surface scientific research take going is an entrepreneur;

- commodity work release organize reach with engaged in entrepreneurs;
- the goods sell, re sell and commerce their work organize reach with engaged in entrepreneurs.

Entrepreneur of labor content how, what is it with is engaged in? About this the following separately note reach can

1. Entrepreneurs work commerce risk with linked, new commerce ideas thinking to find and them current reach methods to prove directed creative is work. Risk taking of entrepreneurship main from the features is one
2. Entrepreneurs work resources - financial funds, raw materials and equipment, personnel and data continuously respectively search, activity attraction reach measures to build directed is work.
3. Entrepreneurship work resources thrift based on reasonable using work release it's a coincidence to show organize to do directed organization is work.

To entrepreneurship person preferences and abilities to himself typical vital expression as view can He is from man entrepreneurship activity for necessary has been adjectives, person nature separately appearances, features demand is enough Usually entrepreneurs for the most necessary to adjectives the following enter:

1. Engaged field according to scientific to departments ownership them always to deepen movement to do

2. To risk based on complicated the decision conditions and finally to information have without being standing up acceptance to do according to initiative ability;
3. Economic processes deep fantastic get, economical events and they are between mutually relationship objective assessment, basic issue second level from issues differentiation of processes the future almost get and different option decisions compare get ability;
4. To laws obedience. Government by issued the law and to procedures strictly submission, his diary in the activity to them compliance of doing high sample show that important at work to others lesson to be
5. Innovation activity, that is product, technology, production release update and others improvement, difficulties overcome ability;
6. Striving for a goal is hard work to labor to lose, to lose, that or this from issues to limitation ready stand up chose on the way hard stand up ability;
7. Organization, from the following consists of:
 - People own after follow get and intended to the goal attraction to achieve, selected of the road correctness them convince know, partners with complicated in the circumstances mutually beneficial to the idea, to the approach reach get ability Partners and hand under of people personal qualities looking work right share get ability;
 - His own work activities reasonable plan get activity;
 - Responsibility, obligation nice reach him do it get
 - Economical fields with together cultural and household areas are also reasonable administration get
8. Economical to be, all of resources saving investigate ready to use be get
9. Own of the word over output, team, partners and society in front of responsibility to be able to feel;
10. Spiritual purity and honesty Honest road with to the goal reach, haram of money Khazar to do, honesty based on work conduct;
11. Spiritual Endurance, own team for combativeness very heavy in tasks himself to the hand take to know.

CONCLUSION

Today, it is a priority to ensure a favorable investment climate in Uzbekistan. The main task of the state is to create a favorable investment environment for attracting capital. Currently, the Republic of Uzbekistan has the opportunity to attract a large

amount of foreign investments: legal documents that reflect guarantees and privileges; the increasing share of the private sector and small business and private entrepreneurship in the economy, state protection of private property and existence of a competitive environment; creation and development of necessary investment infrastructure; political stability; medium level of geographical location; possession of rich natural mineral raw materials; the development of the agricultural sector; availability of cheap and qualified labor resources, etc.

In our opinion, in order to develop the favorable investment environment created in the republic, it is necessary to further strengthen the incentive factors. In this regard, in order to encourage investments in production, it is necessary to give full freedom to business structures in the application of accelerated depreciation methods. In the conditions of the market economy, depreciation is one of the main factors stimulating the investment activity of enterprises. Therefore, in developed countries, the rate of depreciation is determined simultaneously with the approval of the tax rate. In this case, high depreciation rates are set to encourage investment in leading industries. It is important to apply this experience in Uzbekistan, because the average rate of depreciation for machines and equipment is 15% in our country, in the USA it is 20-33%, and in England it is 25%. Strengthening the stimulating role of taxes in the development of a favorable investment environment is of inestimable importance. The stimulating role of taxes can be considered in four aspects, they are: temporary exemption from paying taxes; reduce the tax rate; narrowing of the taxable base; deferment of tax liability (tax credit). The mentioned incentives are applied to a wide range of enterprises with participation of foreign investments to one degree or another. It is necessary to introduce the implementation of incentive tax benefits, as well as investments in human capital, technological growth and development and expansion of technical knowledge. All this puts the issue of modeling the investment environment in Uzbekistan on the agenda. This model creates opportunities to collect perfect information about the factors affecting the foreign investor, to clearly assess the political, economic and social situation and to understand the motivation of foreign partners' actions, and to reform the main means of regulating foreign investments.

REFERENCE

1. Botirjon o'g'li, M. B., Xasanboy, S. D., & Akmaljon o'g'li, A. X. (2022). ISH BILAN BANDLIGINI OSHIRISHDA MEHNAT BOZORINING TA'SIRI. *PEDAGOGS jurnali*, 12(1), 4-10.
2. Botirjon o'g'li, M. B., & Hasanboy o'g'li, S. D. (2022). Organization and increase of activity of small industrial zones.
3. Muhammadjonov, B. B. O. G. L., & Xudayberdiyev, O. A. (2022). O'ZBEKISTONDA FAOLIYAT YURITAYOTGAN KICHIK SANOAT HUDUDLARI RIVOJLANISHINING ISTIQBOLLARI. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 3(1), 265-273.
4. O'G'LI, M. B. B. (2021). ESTABLISHMENT AND ACTIVITY OF SMALL FREE ECONOMIC ZONES IN THE TERRITORY OF UZBEKISTAN. *International Journal of Philosophical Studies and Social Sciences*, 1(2), 156-159.
5. Abdullayevich, A. O., & Abdullajanovich, U. T. (2021, December). DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN UZBEKISTAN. In *Conference Zone* (pp. 123-128).
6. Хакимов, Б., Талабоев, Х., & Холмирзаев, У. (2021). ВОПРОСЫ УЛУЧШЕНИЯ АНАЛИЗА ОБРАЩЕНИЯ ДОЛГОВОЙ ЗАДОЛЖЕННОСТИ В УСЛОВИЯХ НАПРАВЛЕНИЯ. *Экономика и социум*, (6-2), 441-446.
7. Abdullajanovich, U. T. (2022, March). THE ROLE OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE NATIONAL ECONOMY. In *Conference Zone* (pp. 271-276).